

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF DESSERT TECHNOLOGY FOR SPECIALIZED NUTRITION

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Abstract

In this paper, we consider the development of dessert technology for specialized nutrition, namely, an energy muesli bar enriched with useful substances from vegetable raw materials such as carrots and pumpkin. The purpose of the study is to create a product with high nutritional and energy properties, as well as contributing to improving consumer health. The paper analyzes the nutritional properties of carrots and pumpkins, as well as their effect on the enrichment of the bar with vitamins, minerals and fiber. Formulations are being developed and tested, organoleptic properties and safety parameters of the product are being evaluated. The research is aimed at meeting the needs of people who lead an active lifestyle and those who need an additional source of vitamins and energy.

Keywords: energy muesli bar, specialized nutrition, vegetable raw materials, carrots, pumpkin, vitamin fortification, dietary product, functional nutrition.

Introduction.

In our study, an attempt was made to create a specialized product that is aimed at improving the health of various groups of the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Currently, there is a myth about products that are able to remove toxins and “slags” that accumulate in the body. This theory is refuted by many scientific papers.

They say that, firstly, the body is able to remove unnecessary substances, coping well with this task. This mechanism always works, as it is the most important condition for its vital activity.

Secondly, the body is simply not designed for the accumulation of waste decomposition products, especially toxins.

An analysis conducted by Australian scientists suggests questionable results, such as detox diets. There are few subjects, no control groups and quantitative assessments, and these results cannot be relied upon.

After studying these articles, we recommend developing a product technology that would support the body as a whole, and its organs, such as the liver, kidneys, and intestines in particular, in a normal state. This, in turn, will allow us to say that our product promotes the elimination of harmful substances from the body.

The novelty of the work consists in creating a product that will be useful for the digestive system, which has a long shelf life, is available to the vast majority of buyers, a product that could lie on any table, for example, like bread or even salt.

The relevance of the work lies in the development of a product necessary both for the mass consumer and for specialized groups of the population whose work is associated with harmful industries.

The aim of the work is to create a dessert aimed at improving the health of various groups of the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. Analysis of the sources presented in the list of references and relevant to the topic.

2. Creation of a technological process for the preparation of this dessert.

3. Description of the methods and techniques used in this research work.

A literary review. Currently, due attention is not paid to this topic in the Republic of Kazakhstan. We have found several foreign scientific papers similar to our topic, which are listed in the list of references.

For example:

1. The scientific article "FUNCTIONAL FOOD PRODUCTS AND THEIR PURPOSE" is of an overview nature. Here, the authors pay attention to the prospect of developing such products, as well as their useful properties [4].

2. In the following work "DEVELOPMENT OF A FUNCTIONAL DESSERT USING SECONDARY VEGETABLE RAW MATERIALS", the authors prove the expediency of using secondary vegetable raw materials for dessert dishes [5].

3. The article closest to our topic is called "DEVELOPMENT OF AN INNOVATIVE FORMULATION OF MARSHMALLOWS WITH PREBIOTIC PROPERTIES." The authors have developed an innovative formulation of marshmallows with prebiotic properties [6]. But they used very rare ingredients, which in turn increase the cost of the product itself. In our development, we use readily available ingredients.

Research methods. In our work, the following methods were used to determine the quality of the developed dessert: the content of vitamins and minerals, organoleptic properties and physico-chemical parameters, determination of nutritional value.

1. determination of organoleptic quality indicators – according to GOST 5897-90;

2. dry matter and moisture content – according to GOST 5900-2014;

3. acidity (active and titrated) – according to GOST 5898-87;

4. sugar content – according to GOST 5903-89;

5. determination of the mass fraction of protein – according to GOST 34551-2019;

6. determination of the mass fraction of fat – according to GOST 31902-2012.

The experiments were carried out in special laboratories of the Almaty University of Technology.

Results. The analysis of the obtained data showed that the addition of pumpkin puree makes it possible to obtain a functional product, 100 g of which can satisfy a person's daily need for vitamin A by 14%, and carrot puree by 45%. Honey, grapes, lemon have a beneficial

effect on the body in diseases of the cardiovascular system and digestive organs. 4 samples were with different ratios of components such as honey, carrots, and pumpkin. Sample number 5 was a control sample.

According to the results of the organoleptic evaluation of the samples, a sample was identified that was not inferior to the control sample, and in some ways even ahead of it. This sample is shown at number 4. (see Figure 1 – Diagram of the tasting evaluation of bar samples)

Figure 1 - Tasting evaluation diagram of bar samples

Sample 4 also showed good results in the physicochemical quality assessment. We determined the content of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, dry substances and

acidity (see Figure 2 - Physicochemical composition of samples).

Figure 2 – Physicochemical composition of samples

Thus, based on the data for sample 4, we were able to derive the recipe for our bar (see Table 1 – Bar recipe).

Table 1

Bar recipe		
Name of the raw material	Gross weight, g	Net weight, g
Oatmeal	200	200
Pumpkin	400	280
Carrot	387	290
Raisin	80	80
Honey	100	100
Walnut	43	40
Lemon juice	10	10
Total	1220	1000

Conclusion.

The development we propose, the technology for preparing bars, is intended for a wide range of consumers.

Pumpkin in the composition helps to normalize the gastrointestinal tract;

Carrots contain fiber, which is necessary for the normal functioning of the gastrointestinal tract;

Honey helps the body remove toxins, and also prolongs the shelf life of the bars.

During the development of this product, factors were identified that contribute to an active influence on the body and strengthen the health of various groups of the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

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